

33rd VindKraftNet meeting :: Climate Change

15th April 2026

DTU, Risø, Denmark

Programme

10:00	Welcome and presentation of participants	Lars Landberg, DNV
10:10	Welcome to DTU	Jake Badger, DTU
10:20	How is wind energy meteorology (mis)understood in past and recent studies on climate change's impact on future renewable energy? [01]	Andrea Hahmann, DTU
10:50	Uncertainties in wind resource projections and the economics of wind farm portfolios [02]	Ana Lopez & Kai Lochbihler, Climate Scale
11:40	Method for assessing the impact of climate change on future energy production [03]	Lucas Mackie, Ørsted
12:10	Lunch	
13:10	Climate2Energy: a framework to consistently include climate change into energy system modeling [04]	Jan Wohland, Oslo Uni
13:40	Rain and wind climate co-variation relevant to estimate blade erosion [05]	Abhiram Vinod, Charlotte Hasager, Krystallia Dimitriadou, DTU
14:10	Climate risk analysis in wind resource assessment: how to filter and select climate models? [06]	Anne Lena Holzäpfel, RWE
14:40	Break	
15:10	Impact of Climate Change on 50-year wind speeds and turbine class requirements [07]	Milan Matthew, IUSS Pavia
15:40	Next meeting (place and topic), Zenodo	Lars Landberg, DNV
16:00	End	

Next meeting: At: ???; Topic: measurements; Fall 2026, Organiser: DNV
(lars.landberg@dnv.com)

/LL, 16/04/26

WHEN TRUST MATTERS

CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS ON RENEWABLE ENERGY RESOURCES

Authors:
Gaedana Anamiati (editor), Gerardo Guerra, Lars Landberg,
Pau Mercade, Asuncion Lera St. Clair, Pragya Vishwakarma,
Annika Wybrow

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